

A Case Study on the Backburner Phenomenon in College romantic Relationships at Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng Valenzuela

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ABSTRACT

Many young individuals experience various types of relationships, hoping for a future, comitted, and romantic relationship. Despite their positive intentions, some college students experience prevalent relational problems. Specifically, backburner relationships are those in which one individual is kept as a potential romantic or an option while the relationship remains uncertain or unprioritized. This case study delves into the psychological consequences while having no clear commitment. The researchers conducted 16 structured interviews with college students of Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng Valenzuela who experienced being in a backburner relationship.

The findings of the research using thematic analysis show that individuals often endure psychological pressure, including emotional weariness and diminished self-worth, as well as emotional inconsistency and unpredictable conduct. According to the study, despite a lack of reciprocity, these dynamics are frequently maintained by high levels, of personal commitment , maintenance strategies including "positive illusions", and brief periods of emotional fulfillment . In the end, the study emphasizes "Active Self-Reclamation," the creation of realistic internal boundaries, and the use of outside support networks as crucial tactics for emotional healing and taking back control of oneself.

KEYWORDS

Backburner Relationships, Experiences, Psychological Consequences, Thematic Analysis, College students, Support Networks